

Thomas Adewumi University
Journal of Innovation,
Science and Technology (TAU-JIST)

ISSN: 3043-503X

RESEARCH ARTICLE

INFLUENCE OF DOWNSIZING ON EMPLOYEES' ENGAGEMENT: EVIDENCE FROM THE NIGERIAN BANKING SECTOR

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ARTICLE DETAILS

Article History:
 Received 02 July 2025
 Accepted 05 October 2025
 Available online 10 December 2025

ABSTRACT

In a bit to respond to regulatory pressures, economic volatility and transformation from the realm of technology within the banking system in Nigeria, downsizing has been sought as a recurring strategy. Even though the implementation of downsizing is aimed towards driving efficiency and ensuring reduction in costs, its intending consequences on the engagement of employees remains a principal concern in the human resource parlance. To this end, this study examined how downsizing influences the engagements of employees within the Nigerian banking system. The research was underpinned by the Social Exchange Theory and Psychological Contract Theory. The methodology centers on the adoption of quantitative research design where data were obtained using structured questionnaire that were administered to one hundred and twelve (112) employees of "Guaranty Trust Bank in Alimosho Area of Lagos State". The result provided that downsizing significantly affects employees' engagement in the banking system. Similarly, high degree of association was discovered to exist between downsizing and employees' engagement in the banking system. Through the findings, it was concluded that organisation should apply equity and fairness when embarking on downsizing in order to achieve employees' engagement after the exercise. Equally, the management of the bank (GTB) and other organisation should provide information regarding the implementation of downsizing in order to give employees' sense of belonging and bring about workforce engagement in the banking system.

KEYWORDS

Downsizing, Employees' Engagement, Guaranty Trust Bank

Introduction

For organizations to succeed, there is need to pay more attention to policy that will increase profitability and efficiency, particularly when it has to do

with predicting dynamics of the changing economic policies, and situations so as to compete favourably within global market landscape (Rasak, Ayub, Arzu, & Aslam, 2013). Therefore, employers and employees are expected to fashion out modalities and methods on how

Quick Response Code	Access this article online	
	<p>Website: https://journals.tau.edu.ng/index.php/tau-jist</p>	<p>DOI:</p>

to resolve teething issues like downsizing when organisations are found in such dilemma (Mansur, Sanusi & Triatmanto, 2020; Khan, Nair, & Sharma, 2025). This is because, the contemporary environment of the banking system is faced with rapid advancements in technologies, persistent economic uncertainties and intense competition, which are in combination compelling the adoption of strategic means by financial institutions to improve performance, maintain efficiency and sustainability to ensure overall organisational success (Genty & Olanipekun, 2024).

One of such strategic move is downsizing, which has to do with reduction in workforce, reconfiguring job roles and organisational restructuring. Even though, the rationale tied towards the implementation of downsizing has been viewed as avenues for enhancing cost efficiency, enhancement of organisational survival and so forth, but a critical question on how the remaining employees within such organisation(s) engage with their jobs with rapt attention and full commitments become a riddle requiring critical examination, hence this study.

This explains why organizations irrespective of public or private while introducing modern cost cutting strategies such as downsizing as a corporate policy to reduce cost and to achieve employees' engagement must be mindful of its dysfunctionality, especially on the morale of current employees (Olanipekun et al., 2025; Anekwe et al., 2019). Downsizing is a deliberate management tool that has become a normal event in today's business activities (Bushra, 2010). In essence, as strategic as it seems, it has the potential for undermining the engagement of employees through increased perception of insecurity on the job, diminishing trusts in management and violation of psychological contracts (Shrotryia & Dhanda, 2020). These aftermaths may have adverse influence on the motivation, morale, and commitments of employees, thus, weakening effective delivery of service and organisational effectiveness owing to the fact that the banking system heavily rely on the interaction of human to ensure quality in service (Sikayena, Amoah, & Ankomah, 2016).

Within the Nigerian banking sector, systemic changes like ongoing digital transformation, mergers and acquisitions and regulatory reforms on periodic basis have made downsizing a strategic and recurrent practice in organizations (Saks & Gruman, 2014). In spite of its widespread adoption, there is dearth in empirically validating the degree of influence and relationship subsisting between downsizing and the engagements of employees within this sector. Accordingly, thus study investigated the influence of downsizing on employees' engagement with evidence from employees from the Nigerian banking sector, with the intention to generate context specific insights and perceptions capable of promoting a more sustainable HR practices and informing managerial policies.

Statement of the Problem

The engagement of employees reflects both emotional as well as psychological commitments of employees to their organisational activities. How engaged employees are to work have been acknowledged as a significant driver that is critical towards organisational productivity and performance across diverse sectors globally. This stems from the notion that engagement reveals and reflects employees' dedication, willingness as well as enthusiasm towards contributing above and beyond elementary requirements of their jobs, for the sake of bolstering organisational

competitiveness and sustainability for a long term (Wang, Zhu, Dormann, Song & Bakker (2020). Nonetheless, within the Nigerian banking system, frequent changes like regulatory reforms, internal cost-cutting mechanisms and economic conditions have intensified the rationale for adopting downsizing as a mechanism for survival (Habibi et al., 2023). Downsizing which denotes ensuring of reduction in the staff strength of an organisation as a means to streamline operations, improve competitive positioning and lower costs (Chiosh, 2024; Egbunike & Adeniyi, 2017).

Regardless of its strategic intent and objective, downsizing is often connected with significant operational and psychological consequences, especially for surviving employees (Erum, Abid & Contreras, 2020; Natrajan, Sanjeev & Singh, 2019). Studies have proven that those who have lost their jobs are not the only victims of the effect of downsizing; even the so called survivors still nurse the fear of increased work demands, elevated job security, reduction of insights for fairness, supports, and decline in access towards opportunities for career advancements/developments all of which are central for higher employees' well-being and work engagements (Dlouhy & Casper, 2021; Frone et al., 2020; Anekwe, et al. 2019). Such disadvantageous consequences can result in increased absenteeism, lower morale, reduce affective commitments to work, undermine productivity gains; thus defeating the rationale for which downsizing was initially carried out and diminish loyalty (Nwoye, 2017).

Within the context of the Nigerian banking system, where this study is based, downsizing has been employed as a strategy that is key for reducing costs, especially during periods of consolidation reforms and financial distress; still empirical investigations and validation on how this influences the engagements of employees remain fragmented and sparse. While downsizing from the viewpoint of general organisational performance and financial outcomes have been looked at, only few explorations on how it affects the levels of engagements of surviving employees within Nigerian banks are available (Egbunike & Adeniyi, 2017; Ikechukwu-Ifudu, 2016). This presents a notable literature gap on the account of the fact that there is heavy reliance of banks on human capital to aid excellence in their delivery of service for competitive differentiation in their dynamic industry and environment of operation.

Given the essentiality and reputation of how employees' engagement contributes towards retention, customer service quality, and job performance within the banking system, mastering and comprehending how employees' engagement is influenced by downsizing becomes very imperative both academically and practically. Therefore, this study investigated the influence of downsizing on employees' engagement with evidence from the Nigerian banking sector by filling both contextual and empirical gaps and providing insights that are evidence-based to aid concrete policy decisions, inform HR strategies and enhance leadership practices within the sector.

Study Objective(s)

The study's principal objective was aimed at the investigation of how downsizing influences the engagement of employees' in Guaranty Trust Bank, Lagos, Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives were aimed at:

1. Investigating how downsizing affect employees' engagement in Guaranty Trust Bank; and
2. Examine the relationship between downsizing on employees' engagement in Guaranty Trust Bank.

Hypotheses Formulated for the Study

H0₁: Downsizing has no significant influence on employees' engagement in GTB, Alimosho, Lagos State, Nigeria.

H0₂: There is no significant relationship between downsizing and employees' engagement in GTB, Alimosho, Lagos State, Nigeria.

Conceptual Review

Relevant scholarly literatures were examined under this section to understand downsizing specifically within the Nigerian system of banking. This section the foundations of downsizing as a concept and its influence on the engagement of employees. Furthermore, this section of the investigation provides theoretical guidelines to sufficiently navigate this examination.

Concept of Downsizing

Premised on global events like pressures from the aftermath of COVID-19 and local economic downturn from Nigeria necessitated the rationale for engaging cost-cutting strategies (Inyang & Williams, 2019). Within the Nigerian banking system, numerous policies have also sufficed such as regulatory reforms, and economic shocks, which made downsizing a strategic point of action. This made downsizing a crucial issue in the lexicon of human resource management (Ogunbote, 2018). Downsizing under this study implies a deliberate action targeted at strategically reducing the workforce of an organisation so as to enhance competitiveness, reduce the costs of operations and improve efficiency (Frone & Blais, 2020). In contemporary organisations, downsizing as a concept is no longer perceived as a mere response to crisis but as a mechanism for restructuring connected with automation, strategic realignment and digitalization (Johnstone, 2024).

Insights from the banking sector has states further that downsizing operates in the company of adopting fintech solutions, branch rationalization, pressure due to regulatory compliance and mergers and acquisition. With the above mechanism, banks operating within the Nigerian system are reducing their staff on an increasing basis as a result of the rapid rate at which electronic banking platforms are expanding, with expansion in other areas like agency banking and its models, as well as strategies for optimizing costs have all put downsizing as a repeated experience rather than an event that is extraordinary or exceptional (Sikayena, et al., 2016).

Meanwhile, ever since adopting downsizing as a strategic mechanism by organisations globally, researchers have developed interest for its study. In view of this, to understand the trend like downsizing it becomes necessary to understand how employees' will be loyal and engage to their job after the exercise. It is important to note that the psychologically speaking, the well-being and engagement of surviving employees then becomes a subject for discussion within such environments of work due to its dysfunctionality on these employees (Virick, Lilly & Casper, 2007). For

instance, remaining employees may be faced with unfavorable consequences resulting to having doubts on work assignments, whether new or altered, which could pose a significant strain in the adaptation towards career paths and team changes and if not handle reasonably it will result in reducing employees' engagement (Tsai & Yen, 2008). That is why downsizing is not just about eliminating or reducing the workforce rather engagement of the remaining or surviving employees must be put into considerations on the capability of management in being able to achieve its stated agenda and objectives. Some of the key signs of downsizing include increases in non-standard employment, lean management, outsourcing and privatization of public services (Dlouhy & Casper, 2021).

The manifestation of downsizing consequences within organisations takes numerous forms ranges from layoff of involuntary employees, early retirement programmes, employees' redeployment, schemes to aid voluntary exit, outsourcing of non-core functions/operations emanating from branch closures as a result of digital migration (Appelbaum et al., 2015). Examining modern day literature from the perception of categorization, Nigerian banks engage the practice of downsizing as avenues for redesigning work to involve multi-tasking of roles as a way to intensify performance, changing systemic approaches, all of which increases the prevalence of downsizing where additional workloads are placed on surviving employees which may affect their psyche (Miaoyun & Vane-Ing, 2019). The preceding argument validates the submission of a study by Park et al. (2024) which confirmed that employees' psychosocial well-being is negatively influenced by downsizing. According to that report, employees who survive downsizing largely experience high level of anxiety, depressive symptoms, stress and emotional exhaustion.

The Nigerian system of banking operating under regulatory scrutiny and high performance targets may heighten the effects of downsizing on employees. In consonance with the above, Alhamad and Amirah (2024) opined that reducing a workforce can actually weaken the loyalty of employees and further strain their attachments towards work. Olanipekun and Aborisade, (2019) also advanced that within the Nigerian system of banking, employees fear of losing their jobs, coupled with intensive workloads manifesting from downsizing could further undermine the levels of engagements among the remaining surviving employees.

Employee Engagement

This is a multi-dimensional construct that describes the scale at which employees are behaviourally, emotionally, and physically investing in their jobs as well as their organisations Prathiba, 2016; Welch (2011). In the opinion of Kahn (1990) engagement was conceptualized as the art of controlling, exploiting and harnessing employees' give themselves wholly to their roles at work, which makes them individually express themselves emotionally, physically and cognitively while carrying out their roles at work (Ekpenyoong et al., 2023; Gallup, 2021; Segalla & DeNisi, 2019). This elementary and fundamental insights positions engagement as an active oriented work related state and concept rather than a mere passive attitude (Bititci, 2017).

Present-time scholarship express “employees’ engagement” as a positive, work related and persistent psychological state marked by absorption, dedication, and vigour (Schaufeli et al., 2002). Vigour is a reflection of high degree of energy as well as mental resilience channeled to work, dedication implies having a strong sense of enthusiasm and significance, while absorption refers to the exhaustive attention and concentration towards work activities. This conceptualization is universally embraced within human resource management and organisational behaviour studies, including researches within banking and finance sectors (Mercy & Choudhary, 2019; Bailey, Madden, Alfes & Fletcher, 2017).

Within the context of the Nigerian system of banking, engagement of employees is critical as a result of its demand for high performance, recurring restructuring initiatives, intense competition and technological transformation (Rohamina & Teresita 2020; Amah & Sese, 2018). Highly engaged employees within the banking system have the probability of demonstrating compliance with regulatory standards, proactive service behaviour, and sustained productivity, which are pertinent towards customer trust and organisational stability (Osborne & Mohammad, 2017; Schaufeli, 2017). Within the corridor of the Nigerian banking system, employees’ engagement indicates a pivotal psychological resource which is extremely sensitive to the practices of downsizing. Downsizing rattles cognitive focus, emotional attachment, and discretionary behaviours through perceived injustice, insecurity of jobs and breach in psychological contracts (Lathabhavan, Balasubramanian & Natarajan, (2017). In consequence, having a deep comprehension of what employee engagement symbolizes gives a robust ideology for the examination of human outcomes and repercussions of downsizing and providing a fundamental initiative for the development of sustainable human resource strategies during the post-downsizing period (Patnaik & Dubey, 2019; Bai & Liu, 2018; Saks & Gruman, 2014).

Downsizing and Employees Engagement

Empirical investigations have submitted that a positive association was found between the engagement of employees and retention, job performance and service quality, while disengagement intensifies counterproductive behavioural scope to work and fuels high rate of turnover intentions (Schaufeli, 2017). Analysis from the Nigerian banking system, reduction in the engagement is employees associated with downsizing has been connected with impaired and weakened commitment, huge decline in service quality, and intensified intention to quit among the surviving employees (Ekpeyong et al., 2023). Therefore, the engagement of employees serves as a crucial mechanism of explanation regarding how individual and organisational outcomes are affected by downsizing. Thus, organisational effectiveness on the long-run could be hampered due to the erosion of engagement heralding from downsizing, when not tackled proactively

Empirical investigation intensely suggested that downsizing negatively affect the engagement of surviving employees, this is because it causes disruption in the employment relationship by intensifying uncertainty through the alteration of perceived obligations between employers and their employees. Consequently, this could lead to reduction in employees’ engagement as they use this as a coping strategy in protecting themselves from future perceived threats from their organisations (Frone & Blain,

2020). From the viewpoint of psychological contract, the interpretation of downsizing by employees implies breaching implicit promises relating to the security of jobs, organisational support, and career development (Alhamad & Amirah, 2024). From this submission, when employees discern that management is failing to honour implicit and unwritten obligations, there is an emergence of feelings of betrayal and distrust, which then triggers lower commitments, engagements and organisational citizenship behaviour (Bakker & Albrecht, 2018).

In a similar vein, the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model analysed that decline in engagement resulting from downsizing empahsises changes in the conditions of work. This is because downsizing commonly intensifies job demands, thus, creating role overload, work pressures, and emotional strain, while at the same time bring reduction in job resources, in areas like autonomy, supervisory support, and opportunities for growth. An empirical submission by Bakker and Albrecht, (2018) highlighted that the imbalance and variance between demands and resources can result in reduced work engagement emanating from emotional exhaustion among survivors.

A study by Frone and Blain (2020) where large scale survey data was used, it was discovered that downsizing within an organisation correlates with poorer conditions of work, reduction in job satisfaction and inflated psychological distress. Another study by Sinha Roy (2021) illustrated that repetitive downsizing being experienced by employees can hinder their morale, weaken their emotional attachment to the job, and causes diminished trust in management.

Empirical literature affirms that the negative consequence of downsizing on the engagement of employees cannot be overemphasized but pertinent here is how downsizing is being managed. To this end, Alhamad and Amirah (2024) suggested that factors like perceived fairness, transparent communication and supportive leadership and employees’ involvement are essential ingredients for enhancing employees’ engagement at work in the period of downsizing. Their suggestion brings to fore that it is crucial to invest in the provision of downsizing support machineries in terms of redistribution of workload, counselling, and career development initiatives; all of which can be exploited in preserving employees’ engagement and sustaining performance.

Theoretical Framework

Theory is a well substantiated explanation of an aspect of the natural world that can incorporate laws, hypotheses and facts. In addition, it is an idea used to account for a situation or justify a course of action. This study was anchored on the social exchange theory by Blau (1964) and Homans (1958) and the Psychological Contract Theory by Rousseau, (1995).

Social Exchange Theory

This theory provides a theoretical lens by detailing analysis as to how employees engagement is influenced by downsizing, especially within the Nigerian system. The theory is credited to Homans (1961) and Blau (1964), whose explanations recorded that relationships at work is being governed by the law of reciprocity and exchanges between

employees and their managements. As employees' contribute loyalty, efforts and engagement while expecting a form of reciprocation from the management or organisation using rewards like career opportunities, job security, socio-emotional support and fair treatment. The fulfilment of this reciprocal expectations indicates that employees have high degree of propensity for high engagement; however, its violation can make employees withdraw positive actions and behaviour towards work (Farganis, 2011; Saks, 2006; Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005).

Downsizing signals a disruption to the social exchange connection between employees and their employers. In the Nigerian banking system, the occurrence of downsizing arose due to acquisitions, mergers, regulatory reforms and technological automation. Thus, reducing the workforce on the basis of the above undermines the expectations of employees in areas like stability and job security, which represents primary component of the exchange relationship. From the viewpoint of this theory downsizing indicates an art of withdrawing organisational commitment, thereby establishing disparity and polarity in the exchange relationship (Ikechukwu-Ifudu, 2016; Alfes et al., 2013; Khan, 1990). Insecurity of jobs which is a prominent consequence of downsizing can weaken the norm of reciprocity, which can lead to employees withholding their engagements as a means of self-protecting response due to the alteration in the exchange relationship (Omoruyi et al., 2021; De Cuyper et al., 2020).

Laconically, a compelling explanation has been provided by the SET detailing the negative effect downsizing has on the engagement of employees within the Nigerian banking system. Downsizing is a disruptor of an already established exchange connections by impairing trust, perceived organisational support and job security (Cropanzano, et al., 2017). Thus, when the failure of the organisation in reciprocating their efforts, and loyalty, is perceived by employees their response is communicated through reduction in engagement. This theory thus reinforces the crucial nature of fair downsizing practices, post downsizing support mechanisms, and transparent communication to reinstate balance in the exchange relationship so as to sustain the engagements of employees.

Psychological Contract Theory

This theory provides insights on the outcomes of downsizing with focus on perceived obligations of employees vis-à-vis their expectations relating to their jobs in terms of fair treatment and job security. A widely acknowledged interpretation of downsizing reflects a breach of implicit contracts further resulting in to reduction in trusts, poor morale, and skepticism from surviving employees (Park et al., 2024). From the perspective of the Nigerian banking system which believes in ascribing immense value to long-term form of employment and which has been traditionally recognized, thus, breaching this form of contract breeds negativism which leads to pernicious attitude and destructive behaviour of employees heralding as a consequence of downsizing.

This theory provides a framework that is robust in detailing how employees engagement is being influenced by the concept of downsizing, especially within the Nigerian system of banking where reduction in workforce and restructuring exercise have become recurrent activities (Robbinson & Rousseau, 1994). This

theory infer the subjective belief employees hold towards the mutually shared obligations existing between them and their organisation (employer), which involves fair treatment, job security, organisational support and career development (Rousseau, 1995). Dissimilar to formal employment contracts, the psychological contract is socially constructed and implicit, which distinguishes it and makes it more delicate towards organisational actions like downsizing and this is because of the fundamental shift it signals in both employment relationships and organisational priorities (Bal et al., 2013).

Within the context of the Nigerian system of banking, downsizing has resulted in intensified insecurity of jobs, decline in moral of surviving employees and diminished trust of the employees in their management. This outcome presents a reflection and a preponderance shift from affinity or kinship to transactional psychological contract, where focus is now narrowly placed on immediate gratifications and rewards rather than the demonstration of long-term commitment (Guest & Conway, 2004). In consequence, employees may likely continue performing their required tasks but may be psychologically extricated and estranged, which could undermine productivity, organisational effectiveness and service delivery.

Methodology

Research Design: For this study, the researchers chose the descriptive survey and research design, this assist them in adequately selecting a well representative sampling frame from the bank's overall population.

Population: The study population includes all Guaranty Trust Bank (GTB) staff in Alimosho Local government area in Lagos State, which is two hundred and ninety-eight (298) according to human resource department of the Bank.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique: In line with Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sampling size determination table, a sample size of one hundred and sixty-nine (169) respondents was drawn from the population, using purposive sampling method.

Data Collection Instrument: 8-items questionnaire by Ndlovu & Brijball (2005) on downsizing and 10-items scale on employee engagement developed by Passanan, Waiphot and Kwanta (2018) were adapted for the study. Thereafter, the instruments were subjected to test-re-test method and reliability co-efficient of 0.72 was obtained for downsizing and 0.76 for employee engagement. The questionnaire was formatted on four (4) point Likert's type rating scale: ranging from Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1).

Data Collection Procedure: The copies of the questionnaire were administered personally by the researcher with the help of three experienced research assistants. One hundred and sixty-nine (169) copies of the questionnaire were distributed; one hundred and thirty-one (131) copies retrieved but only one hundred and twelve (112) copies which represent sixty-seven-point eight percent (67.8%) were certified valid for analysis.

Method of Data Analysis: Data were analysed using regression analysis and correlation analysis to test the stated hypotheses. Regression was used in testing the effect while correlation was

employed to measure the level of relationship between the independent and dependent variable.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

H01: Downsizing has no significant effect on employees’ engagement in GTB, Alimosho, Lagos State, Nigeria.

Table I: Model Summary of regression analysis on the effect of downsizing on employees’ engagement in GTB, Alimosho, Lagos State, Nigeria.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	F	Sig.
1	.901 ^a	.828	.828	.579	1305.806	.000 ^b

The extent at which downsizing affect employee engagement in GTB, Alimosho, Lagos State, Nigeria was presented by the summary table above. The coefficient of determination (R²= 0.901, p-value <0.05) illustrated that 90.1% variation in employee engagement in the selected study area was as a result of downsizing. Based on the above result, it was discovered that downsizing significantly affects employees’ engagement in GTB, Alimosho, Lagos State, Nigeria. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Hypothesis Two

H02: There is no significant relationship between workers downsizing and employees’ engagement in Guaranty Trust Bank (GTB) Alimosho, Lagos State, Nigeria.

Table II: Result of correlation downsizing and employees’ engagement in Guaranty Trust Bank (GTB), Alimosho, Lagos State, Nigeria

		DOWN_SIZ	EMPL_ENG
DOWN_SIZ	Pearson Correlation	1	.565**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.005
	N	112	112
EMPL_ENG	Pearson Correlation	.565**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.005	
	N	112	112

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Above result establishes the relationship between downsizing and employees’ engagement in Guaranty Trust Bank (GTB) Alimosho, Lagos State, Nigeria. The result showed the relationship was positive and statistically significant (r=.565, p<.05). The null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between downsizing and

employees’ engagement was rejected which implies that there is significant relationship between downsizing and employee’s engagement in Guaranty Trust Bank (GTB) Alimosho, Lagos State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Results

The study examined the downsizing and employees’ engagement in Guaranty Trust Bank (GTB) Alimosho, Lagos State, Nigeria.

The hypothesis which stated that downsizing has no significant effect on employees’ engagement in GTB, Alimosho, Lagos State, Nigeria. Finding proved otherwise and this hypothesis was rejected. The finding is in alliance with the position of a study by Singh, Siddiqui, Dewangan and Shrivastava, (2020) which discovered that downsizing does not only affect employees’ engagement, it also negatively impact on their loyalty and causes negative shifts in perception. The outcome of the analysis further supports the position of Angayarkanni and Shobana, (2020) who concluded in their study that downsizing can result in decreased morale, lack of trust, and perceived hostility via poor organisational support, while the survivors may experience survivors’ guilt coupled with increased workload. The finding of this study aligns with the view of Genty and Olanipekun, (2024) whose study highlighted that employee engagements in modern organisations may be hampered by organizational forces such as downsizing or lack of open communication. This study also agree with the position of Dike, (2023) whose study submitted that downsizing negatively affect employees performance and productivity in the Aluminum industry. Ut further aligns with the conclusion by Olanipekun et al. (2025) whose study claimed that prioritizing engagement can help establish psychological safety among employees; this means that even while trying to downsize, considerations must be provided on employees’ general well-being.

The study hypothesis proposed which stated that no significant association between downsizing and employees’ engagement was rejected. The results showed that there is a significant relationship between downsizing and employees’ engagement in in Guaranty Trust Bank (GTB) Alimosho, Lagos State, Nigeria. According to the outcome of the study, downsizing will affect employee engagement because job security is not guarantee as a result of economic challenges and organisation manpower needs at the moment. The result corroborate the study of Rehman and Naeem (2012) who found that downsizing affect employees’ loyalty, perception, and their commitments toward the organization and also result in the poor performance of the organization. Equally, the result aligns with social exchange theory by Blau (1964) and Homans (1958). Social exchange theory is a cost-benefit analysis that evaluates the risks and rewards of continuing or putting an end to a relationship. According to the theory, employees’ compare the benefit he/she is receiving from the employer and what his/her contribution in terms of being engage to the work or not. For example, when employees receive good salary, recognition and opportunities to further his education from the organisation, they feel indebted to respond in kind and “repay” the organization and by being engaged and loyal to the work. In view of this, downsizing of workforce as a cut cost strategy adopt by organisation may affect employees’

engagement. This findings is in congruence with the position of Genty et al. (2025) which stated that management must make the environment of work very enjoyable, so that even in the face of imminent downsizing, the climate of the environment can be more stimulating and still keep employees fully engaged without any fear of the unknown.

Conclusion

From the study's outcome, it was revealed that downsizing profoundly exerts significance and immense influence of the engagement of employees under the Nigerian system of banking. While these organisations engage downsizing as a strategic mechanism for responding to pressures emanating from costs, regulatory demands and digital transformation, its dysfunctional effects on human is severe and enduring. The study conclusively provided that downsizing practices that are comes abruptly, and which were poorly communicated are perceived to foster loss of trust, thus, further undermining intensification of job insecurity, employees psychological contacts and erosion of management's trust. As a result, pertinent dimensions of employees' engagements like absorption, dedication and vigour are weakened. In conclusion, a relationship between downsizing and employees' engagement among the workers in the study. The significance of this result is that employees' engagement can only be achieved when there is a friendly policy towards the workforce by the organisation. In addition, employees may accept downsizing strategy when there is fairness and equity in the procedure used by the organisation.

Significantly, the study's finding obtained that the negative and dysfunctional consequences of downsizing cannot be avoided. Comprehensively speaking, it can be concluded that downsizing within the Nigerian banking system should not be treated with a kid-glove as its consequences are far reaching with huge negative implications on the surviving employees. Banks failing to manage both psychological and social dimensions of downsizing are under huge risks, which are capable to undermine efficiency gains, productivity upon the reason as to why downsizing activities was embarked upon. Alignment of sustainable performance is thus dependent on the calibration of decisions towards downsizing with conscious efforts that places deliberate focus on engagement of employees for the sake of preserving trust, employee well-being and fairness.

Recommendations

Based on the outcome of the research, the study recommends that:

Managements of Guaranty Trust Bank (GTB) should apply equity and fairness when embarking on downsizing in order to achieve employees' engagement after the exercise.

In addition, in as much as downsizing is one of defensive strategies for the organisation.

Employers must establish a sense of belonging to their workforce and bring about employees' engagement and loyalty.

Management must initiate a process of transparency in communicating and implementing strategies to downsize; so as to foster greater loyalty from employees.

Components such as leadership communication, opportunities for skill development, organizational support, engagement initiatives, favourable organisational culture hinged on employee recognition, should be employed by management in mitigating the negative influence of downsizing on the engagement of employees' engagement.

Contributions to Knowledge

Our contributed to the practice by revealing the importance of downsizing as significant mechanism deployed by organisations to survive in the dynamic business terrain and sail trough in times of economic or regulatory challenges.

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